

PROGRESS IN COUPLING COMPUTATIONAL THERMODYNAMICS AND COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS TO SUPPORT MOLTEN SALT REACTOR APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Progress on the development of multi-physics capabilities by coupling computational fluid dynamics and computational thermodynamics codes for Molten Salt Reactor applications. This work is part of the SAMOSAfer project and is intended to support on capability development with applications related to reactor safety, including over-heating and under-cooling scenarios. A one-way coupling scheme between OpenFOAM and Thermochemica is demonstrated through a solidification process of the MSFR, where phase accountancy and influence of solid salt formation are shown. The Joint Research Centre-Karlsruhe Molten Salt Database (JRCMSDB) is used as input to thermodynamic calculations and expected future applications are discussed. This is the first step of a long-term plan for a two-way coupling and this paper presents progress towards this goal.

1. Introduction

The Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR) is a fast-spectrum molten salt reactor design being studied in the framework of the European SAMOSAfer project (<https://samosafer.eu/>). The main objective of this reactor design is to burn spent fuel from other reactors and minor actinides due to the use of a fast spectrum and liquid fuel and coolant. The SAMOSAfer project is primarily a European consortium and Ontario Tech University divided into several Work Packages (WP) to study a vast number of different topics related to MSR safety. This study is in direct support of the WP2, which focuses on the study of fuel salt retention.

The focus of this study is to present recent progress on a multi-physics numerical coupling between Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Computational Thermodynamics (CT) to investigate fuel salt transport and chemistry for under-cooling scenario solidifies molten salt and the flow dynamics is altered. The solidification process is present in the molten salt spill accident, which was identified by the Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) - Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) [1] as an important accident scenario requiring further investigation.

The solidification process can be a final step of other abnormal conditions, such as an overheating scenario. The MSFR design has multiple freeze plugs installed at the bottom of the reactor core [2] [3]. These valves act as a form of containment of small portions of continuously frozen molten salts that melt when the reactor coolant reaches a certain temperature. This safety equipment allows all the coolant to be quickly drained to a containment tank, where it can be safely frozen. However, the study of such scenarios is complex and can be simulated via multi-physics, which is the focus of this work.

The numerical coupling between CFD and CT is one alternative to study such scenarios and has been used for some metallurgical processes [4]. The study of Ersson *et al.* [5] involved the coupling of the CFD code Fluent [6] and CT code Thermo-Calc [7]. were coupled to analyze the decarbonization of liquid steel when reacted to a pure oxygen injection. The coupling method allowed Ersson *et al.* to simulate the flow dynamics of the chemical reaction, the production of slag, carbon monoxide, and other species along the time and how each phase influenced the decarbonization process [5]. The partial pressure of carbon monoxide could be monitored to estimate the carbon concentration of steel along the time.

Ersson *et al.* [5], especially about how the mass balance and volume fraction update were made along with the results from Thermo-Calc, how the production of gases was allocated for cells previously filled with liquid-phase, and how accurate the decarbonization process was when instant chemical equilibrium is assumed when compared to experimental data. This point is relevant since the simplification of reaction kinetics could result in large errors, but these were not observed due to the high temperatures and fast mixing due to turbulence. Secondary recommendations were made to optimize the calculation process since CFD and CT coupling can significantly increase the total amount of simulation time. The adoption of the Volume of Fluid (VoF) [8] multiphase simulation is more appropriate since just one averaged momentum and energy equation need to be calculated, instead of one set of equations for every single specie being calculated by Thermo-Calc [7]. Along the chemical equilibrium calculations, dozens of species may appear and the solution for all of them may be prohibitive and unstable.

It is worth noting that specific studies to optimize coupling between CFD and CT can be found [9] [10] [11], other applications of CFD coupled with CT [12] [13], using ChemApp as a CT tool [14] and OpenFOAM as a CFD tool [15]. Specific studies where the coupling method was adopted to study the solidification process [16] [17] identified some of the expertise used in this study.

This project will use OpenFOAM as a CFD tool due to the broad availability of libraries needed and alignment of other SAMOSAFER studies. As a CT tool, Thermochemica [18] is used due to several reasons. The open-source availability, it was specifically designed for direct integration into multi-physics codes where performance considerations are more important, the use of most recent and adequate thermodynamic model for molten salts, the Modified Quasi-chemical (MQM) [19] [20] [21] [22], and compatibility with the JRCMSDB [23], a protective chemistry database that allows all chemical equilibrium calculation of molten salts involved in the MSFR.

This study shows preliminary results of a one-way coupling between the mentioned codes, specifically applied for the solidification process of a molten salt and further expectancy in future studies are discussed.

2. Methodology

2.1 CFD Model

OpenFOAM is a CFD library where it is possible to solve the continuity, momentum and energy equations for a determined system and analyze the fluid transport and heat and mass transfer. It is also possible to expand this approach for multiphase flow through different techniques.

This study focuses on the solidification process of molten salts using the *icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoam* solver, available on the OpenFOAM v2106. This solver is based on the Volume of Fluid (VoF) technique, where each phase is immiscible and a clear boundary between each phase is calculated. In addition, the VoF approach averages one energy and one set of momentum equations for all adopted phases, which is interesting since future analyses will consider dozens of phases. This is not the case for a Eulerian-Eulerian approach, which considers different momentum and energy equations for each phase, which could result in a time-prohibitive analysis and high numerical instability during the solution process. Equations 1 to 13 better describe the VoF in the *icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoam*.

Continuity Equation:

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where \vec{u} is the velocity vector.

Volume Fraction Equation:

$$\frac{\delta \alpha_L}{\delta t} = -\vec{\nabla} \cdot (\alpha_L \vec{u}) - \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u} \alpha_L (1 - \alpha_L) \quad (2)$$

Where α_L is the liquid phase fraction, t is time.

Sharpening Velocity:

$$\vec{u} = C |\vec{u}| \frac{\vec{\nabla} \alpha_L}{|\vec{\nabla} \alpha_L|} \quad (3)$$

where C is the inertial resistance.

Phase Fraction Balance:

$$\alpha_L + \alpha_s = 1 \quad (4)$$

where α_s is the solid phase fraction.

Momentum Equation:

$$\rho \frac{\delta}{\delta t} \vec{u} = -\rho \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\vec{u}\vec{u}) - \vec{\nabla} P + (\mu + \mu_t) \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left[(\vec{\nabla} \vec{u} + \vec{\nabla} \vec{u}^T) - \frac{2}{3} (\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u}) \vec{I} \right] - \frac{2}{3} \rho k \vec{I} + \rho \vec{g} + \vec{F}_{surf} \quad (5)$$

where, ρ is the mixed density, μ is the mixed viscosity, μ_t is the turbulent mixed viscosity, k is the turbulent kinetic energy, \vec{g} is the gravity vector, \vec{F}_{surf} is the surface tension between phases.

Surface Tension:

$$\vec{F}_{surf} = \vec{\nabla} \bar{\tau}_{surf} \quad (6)$$

where $\bar{\tau}_{surf}$ is the surface stress tensor.

Surface Stress Tensor:

$$\bar{\tau}_{surf} = \sigma \left(|\vec{\nabla} \alpha_L| \vec{I} - \frac{\vec{\nabla} \alpha_L \cdot (\vec{\nabla} \alpha_L)^T}{|\vec{\nabla} \alpha_L|} \right) \quad (7)$$

where σ is the surface tension between the liquid and –solid phases.

Energy Equation

$$\rho \frac{\delta E}{\delta t} = -\rho \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u} E + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\lambda \vec{\nabla} T + \vec{\tau} \cdot \vec{u}) \pm S_h \quad (8)$$

where E is the mixed energy, λ is the thermal conductivity

Effective Density:

$$\rho = \alpha_s \rho_s + \alpha_L \rho_L \quad (9)$$

Effective Viscosity:

$$\mu = \alpha_s \mu_s + \alpha_L \mu_L \quad (10)$$

Effective Conductivity:

$$\lambda = \alpha_s \lambda_s + \alpha_L \lambda_L \quad (11)$$

Effective Energy:

$$E = \frac{\alpha_s \rho_s E_s + \alpha_L \rho_L E_L}{\rho} \quad (12)$$

It is important to state that the *icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoam* uses the Lee mass transfer model to calculate the solidification (or also melting) process, better described in [24] and the original formulation of Lee [25], as shown in Equation 13,

$$m = C' \rho \alpha \frac{T - T_A}{T_A} L \quad (13)$$

where m is the mass transfer between phases, C' is Lee's model constant, T is the current temperature, T_A is the solidification or melting temperature, L is the latent heat. It is worth noting that the same set of equation works for both solidification ($T < T_A$ and C' negative) and melting ($T > T_A$ and C' positive). C' , L and T_A are defined by the user.

2.2 Gibbs Energy Minimizer (GEM)

The numerical technique of GEM was originally proposed by White, Johnson and Dantzig [26], which is based on identifying a unique combination of species and phases that yield a minimum in the integral Gibbs of a closed isothermal isobaric system from among the many possible candidates. The integral Gibbs energy of a multicomponent, multiphase system is represented in Equation 14,

$$G_{system} = RT \left(\sum_{\lambda'=1}^{\Lambda} n_{\lambda'} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\lambda'}} x_{i(\lambda')} \tilde{\mu}_i + \sum_{\omega=1}^{\Omega} n_{\omega} \tilde{\mu}_{\omega} \right) \quad (14)$$

where R [J / mol K] is the ideal gas constant, T [K] is the absolute temperature, $n_{\lambda'}$ denotes the number of species in the solution phase λ' and $x_{i(\lambda')}$ represents the mole fraction of species i in solution phase λ' . Λ and ω represent the number of stable solution phases and stoichiometric phases respectively and the number of moles in the solution phase λ' and stoichiometric phase ω are denoted by $n_{\lambda'}$ and n_{ω} [mol] respectively. Finally, $\tilde{\mu}_i$ and $\tilde{\mu}_{\omega}$ represent the dimensionless chemical potential of species i in solution phase λ' and stoichiometric phase ω respectively.

Therefore, to achieve thermodynamic equilibrium, the chemical potential for each component must be uniform throughout the system at thermodynamic equilibrium. In this way, the Gibbs energy of the system needs to be expressed in terms of the element potentials, Γ_j [J/mol], and the number of moles, b_j [J] of the system components, which can be in Equation 15.

$$G_{system} = \sum_{j=i}^{C''} \Gamma_j b_j \quad (15)$$

where C'' denotes the number of system components which is normally the number of elements in the system.

Finally, achieving thermochemical equilibrium in a system requires the three necessary conditions to be satisfied: conservation of mass, Gibbs phase rule, and the Gibbs' Criteria, briefly described below through Equations 16 to 18.

2.2.1 Conservation of Mass

Conservation of mass requires that the mass of element j , b_j , must satisfy the following mass balance in Equation 16,

$$b_j = \sum_{\lambda'=1}^{\Lambda} n_{\lambda'} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\lambda'}} x_{i(\lambda')} v_{i,j} + \sum_{\omega=1}^{\Omega} n_{\omega} v_{\omega} \quad (16)$$

where $v_{i,j}$ and v_{ω} represent the stoichiometric coefficients of element j in solution phase species i and stoichiometric phase ω respectively.

2.2.2 Gibbs' Phase Rule

The Gibbs' Phase Rule defines the thermodynamic degrees of freedom of the system by Equation 17.

$$F = C'' - \Phi + 2 + \Xi \quad (17)$$

where F represents the degrees of freedom, C'' denotes the number of components in the system, Φ denotes the number of phases and Ξ denotes the number of ionic phases.

2.2.3 Gibbs' Criteria

For thermodynamic equilibrium, the Gibbs energy of a system needs to be its global equilibrium. For this, the chemical potential for each system component must have the same value in all stable phases within the system [27], where the chemical potential of any constituent in a stable phase can be defined as a linear function of the element potentials, Γ_j , as shown in Equation 18,

$$\mu_i = \sum_{j=1}^{c''} v_{i,j} \Gamma_j \quad (18)$$

The aforementioned conditions are used in Gibbs energy minimizers to find a unique combination of phases that are stable in the system.

However, as the Gibbs energy function of a system is often non-convex and global optimisation schemes must be used to verify that the converged results from thermodynamic equilibrium codes yield a true global minimum and not a false positive. For this reason, it is required that the chemical potentials of all stable solution phase species and stoichiometric phases abide by the above equality, which is equivalent to Gibbs energy of the system being at a local minimum, and that the conservation of mass and the Gibbs phase rule are satisfied. The sufficient condition requires that all the metastable phases abide by the following conditions are represented by Equation 19 and 20.

$$\pi_{\lambda} = \min_{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\lambda}} x_{i(\lambda)} (\mu_{i(\lambda)} - \sum_{j=1}^c v_{i,j} \Gamma_j) \quad (19)$$

i.e., there must exist a Gibbs' plane such that the element potentials lie on the plane and the chemical potentials of all the species lie on or above the plane and the mole fraction of the species must satisfy the following constraints

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\lambda}} x_{i(\lambda)} = 1 \\ x_{i(\lambda)} \geq 0 \forall i \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

i.e., the sum of mole fraction of all the species in a phase λ must be unity and that the individual mole fractions must be greater than or equal to zero.

For the present study, Thermochemica is used to calculate the global Gibbs energy minimization using the Modified Quasichemical Model in Quadruplet Approximation (MQMQA) thermodynamic model to calculate the chemical equilibrium for molten salt compositions, as demonstrated by [28]. It was possible to calculate the heat capacity of pure liquid and pure solid phases, the onset temperature of melting and enthalpy of fusion for the determined compositions.

2.3 Coupling Method, the *icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoamT*

The numerical coupling between OpenFOAM and Thermochemica is illustrated in Figure 1 and will be called by *icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoamT* from now on. First, several preliminary calculations are made in Thermochemica to calculate the melting temperature and enthalpy of fusion for pure FLiNaK.

As previously described, Thermochemica only requires temperature, pressure, composition, and an appropriate thermodynamic database as input. The JRCMSDB [23] consists of Gibbs energy models for several salts systems of interest for molten salt reactors technology. The current version of the database, named (JRCMSDB), contains over 70 binary systems describing the key fluoride and chloride fuel, and coolant salt mixtures considered for MSRs. The database is continuously developed and extended, and it is expected that the database will evolve throughout the course of the SAMOSAFER project.

In this step, M represents the number of mols of each component adopted in the system. Thermochemica's results are manually set in OpenFOAM files repositories and the *icoReactingMulti-phaseInterFoamT* can be set.

The CFD solver starts and has many steps to achieve a converged time step. At the end of it, Thermochemica is called, and for every cell, temperature, pressure, and composition for every cell are used as input. The JRCMSDB is also used for all calculations. Thermochemica's results are organized and summed so that the contour plot of desired phases in the liquid and solid-state can be post-processed and visualized.

Figure 1: One-way numerical coupling between OpenFOAM v2106 and Thermochemica

2.4 Computational Domain, Boundary Conditions, and Solution Criteria

The computational domain for this demonstration problem is a two-dimensional geometry of the MSFR [29], with dimensions of 2.2 by 2.2 meters, illustrated in Figure 2. The mesh generated counts with 10,750 elements. As previously mentioned, the VoF approach captures the exact

boundary between phases, so this model needs to be discretized enough to capture each boundary, otherwise, the solution becomes unstable and diverge. This can be understood as a disadvantage relative to Eulerian-Eulerian solvers, where a fine discretization is not needed, but more equations must be solved.

Figure 2: 2D MSFR computational domain, boundary conditions and mesh.

Two moving cold walls (710 K) were assumed at -2.5 m/s to simulate a simplified condition of the MSFR heat exchanger and pumping. This were mainly assumed to observe once the moving wall is frozen, how fast the molten salt motion stops. The initial domain temperature was 750 K to give enough time until reach the melting temperature to correctly calculate momentum equations before the solidification starts. The standard $k - \epsilon$ turbulence model was used.

The transient solution criteria were based on fixed time steps of 0.025 s for a total of 240 s. No specific spatial or temporal convergence study was made for this demonstration problem, but reasonable values were adopted; however, a more detailed convergence study will be required for more complex analysis. It is also worth noting that when VoF is adopted, a reasonable mesh converge cannot be reached since as the elements are made smaller, more phase boundaries are calculated, leading to a different flow dynamic, until the simulation diverges due to overflow. For this reason, a balance must be reached, because excessively coarse elements may omit general phase dispersion.

The solution for each time step was defined when the root mean square for the residual equations was smaller than 10^{-4} .

2.5 Thermophysical and Thermochemistry Properties of FLiNaK

This study used FLiNaK as a liquid (LiF-NaF-KF, 46.5-11.5-42 mol %) due to the great availability of studies stating thermophysical properties like density, thermal conductivity, and viscosity [30]. Table 1 summarizes the material properties used in this simulation.

Table 1: Thermophysical and chemical properties of FLiNaK

Property	Unit	FLiNaK	Reference
C_p	kJ/KgK	1750	[30]
$T_{melting}$	K	726	Thermochemica
h_{fusion}	kJ/kg	215.6	Thermochemica
k	W/mK	0.9	[30]
μ	$Pa \cdot s$	0.01	[30]
Density	kg/m^3	2100	[30]

Heat capacity, thermal conductivity, viscosity, density are temperature-dependent properties that can later be substituted by functions and can be used in more complex analyses. Melting temperature and enthalpy of fusion were obtained from Thermochemica, which also shows similar values available in the literature [30]. This was done to demonstrate capabilities of Thermochemica for this study, which can also be used for other systems not available in the literature.

3. Results and Discussion

The initial temperature (750 K) was slowly decreased until elements near the heat exchanger started to solidify. Solidification started between 60 to 70 seconds and formed a complete solid film around 180 seconds. As the frozen film of FLiNaK created a barrier between the velocity wall and the domain, the fluid velocity is rapidly decreased.

This scenario could be understood as an overcooling condition to try to rapidly cool down the reactor core and stop convection. Figure 3 illustrates multiple contour plots at 100 seconds. Figure 3-(A) shows the contour plot of velocity, re-scaled to a maximum velocity of 0.5 m/s for a better visualization near the heat exchanger. As the solid film of salt is being formed, the heat exchanger walls impose downward velocity, dispersing small fractions of solids to the fluid domain.

In Figure 3-(B), the white to gray region shows the temperature range where liquid and solid phases can be found together. Orange colour is pure liquid and light to dark blue is pure solid region. In addition, Figure 3-(C) shows the phase fraction of solid FLiNaK, which is the sum of all three phases that compose it (LiF-NaF-KF, LiF-NaF and NaF-KF). Figure 3-(D), shows the solid phase component fraction NaF among the three solid phases that compounds solid FLiNaK. This contour

plot is shown just to illustrate the capability to map where each phase component is located. It can be useful specifically to track noble metals, rare earth materials and fission products.

OpenFOAM would only be able to calculate where pure solid and liquid phases are present, however, when coupled with Thermochemica, additional phases can be distinguished. It is possible to map each phase and its components, or the sum of them. Figure 3-(C) shown the mol fraction concentration per cell of NaF. Similar plots can be made for other components, such as LiF, KF and NaF.

Figure 3: Contour plot of velocity (A), temperature (B), solid FLiNaK phase fraction (C) and NaF phase fraction (D) at 100 s.

This is interesting because more complex system can be calculated, where fission products, noble metals, and rare earth materials can be tracked and have their concentrations calculated for the entire domain. As an example of this, concentrations of all phases that form solid FLiNaK are calculated along the time and shown in Figure 4.

As previously stated, the solidification behaviour started around 60 to 70 seconds. The legend of Figure 4 shows two different curves for the solid phase “*average alpha solid*”, predicted by OpenFOAM and “*average FLiNaK_Solid*”, predicted by Thermochemica. They show different curves for solid-phase formation because the curve predicted by Thermochemica takes under consideration the two-phase phase region of liquid and solid FLiNaK (incongruent melting), while OpenFOAM only considered the pure solid region, calculated from one transition temperature

(congruent melting). At some point, all solid mixed in the liquid phase would reach the offset temperature and both curves would match. This is a clear example where the aimed two-way coupling will be useful, where incongruent melting will be implemented into *icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoamT* and a more accurate behaviour would be calculated.

Figure 4: Transient phase accountability of solid phases.

At 180 s, the cold moving walls have a complete thin layer of solid salt, which stops the forced convection. The whole solidification behaviour took approximately 200 seconds, for a temperature difference of 40 K (750 K to 710 K).

4. Conclusion and Future Work

Recent progress in the capability development coupling OpenFOAM and Thermochemica for molten salt reactors using a one-way coupling demonstration scenario was shown. The present study shows that one-way coupling can identify which phases are predicted to be stable in the system, which allows one to predict phase transformations possibly near walls or in the bulk liquid flow, which is not possible using standard OpenFOAM solvers.

Future work will focus on two-way coupling where Thermochemica will provide information directly to OpenFOAM to predict phase transformations and other thermodynamic properties. Currently, just one phase change can be calculated at a time with OpenFOAM if a two-way coupling is reached, mixing phases with independent transport properties can be considered, which is interesting for a more accurate behaviour during change-of-state scenarios in most MSR designs.

The present solver can also help to model molten salt spill accidents, raised by the ORNL PIRT for molten salt reactors [1]. More complex systems can be used in further scenarios using the current coupling, especially considering noble metals and rare earth materials, which are partially available in the JRCMSDB.

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Disclaimer

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Data Availability Statement

All figures, raw data, numerical solver and demonstration problem here presented can be found in [31] and <https://github.com/nikolasscuro/icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoamT>, where it can be find updated. The JRCMSDB is a proprietary database and are only available under request and analysis.

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